

Corporate Social Responsibility Initiatives of Rashtriya Ispat Nigam Limited during COVID-19

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ABSTRACT

Corporate Social Responsibility has become one of the catchphrases of new millennium across the world and the corporate as well as government must take care of it. Corporate social responsibility has also been interpreted as the concept of triple bottom line i.e. people, planet and profit, which captures the expanded spectrum of values and criteria such as economic, environmental and social for measuring organizational success. In view of this RINL has been taken various CSR initiatives like education, health care, skill development, financial assistance and sanitation during covid-19. The main aim of this study is to examine effectiveness and level of satisfaction of beneficiaries, the CSR initiatives of RINL during Covid-19. During three months from March to May 2020 RINL has done many programmes to help the poor to severe and overcoming pandemic situation. Findings of the study revealed that majority of people, who have benefited and observed they are very much satisfied with the welfare programmes of RINL especially, during lockdown period.

Keywords: Corporate Social Responsibility, health care, skill development, triple bottom line, Covid-19

INTRODUCTION

Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) has been attracting attention recently by the corporate world worldwide. The corporations discharge their CSR through social development in various ways in varying degree. However, the practice of CSR has also attracted controversy and criticism. There are two opposing arguments: firstly, the corporations profit in manifold ways by spending on CSR projects. Secondly, CSR is criticized and opposed in that it makes the corporations deviate from their primary economic roles in doing business. This debate and criticism revolve around the basic objectives of the firm. Modern scholars have proposed many different objectives for firms which again are also abound with raging controversy and criticism. The primary objective of an economy and synthesizes the hitherto different objectives with CSR to get a holistic view. This will not only put the controversy regarding the objectives of the firm but also has interesting implications for the recent corporate social responsibility of business, environmental concerns, and questions the need for a separate theory of public firm as well.

Various CSR initiatives undertaken by RINL has benefited, the people who are residing in villages at plant in ways education, health care, skill development, financial assistance and sanitation are initiatives help poor through welfare schemes during pandemic situation of covid-19. Further, this study would help in understanding the benefits and present situation of various CSR programmes of RINL. For this purpose I am very much interested to do this study.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Samuel O. Idowu (2007), with their study of twenty companies in U.K., propounded that the U.K. companies has now become ethical in the content of social responsibility as companies disclose its CSR with a view of public benefits, government request and issue information to stakeholders because the companies think that stakeholders of twenty first century are better educated them past.

According to Porter and Kramer (2006), there is a lack of success with the company's efforts related to CSR in improving business results. Better link of CSR with key business source allows employers to recognize that it can be a source of: opportunities, innovation and competitive advantage. CSR is related to the incorporation of reason able policies in corporate strategy, culture and daily decision making, consecutively to meet the needs of stakeholders. This is related to the creation of company strategy and successful brands (Wether and Chandler 2004).

Research Objectives

- 1) To study the effectiveness of Corporate Social Responsibility initiatives of Rashtriya Ispat Nigam Limited during COVID-19.
- 2) To analyze the impact of Corporate Social Responsibility initiatives of Rashtriya Ispat Nigam Limited during COVID-19.

Hypotheses

H₁= Financial assistance, social helping and other programmes are positive opinion of CSR initiatives of RINL during COVID -19.

H₂= Education programmes are positive opinion of CSR initiatives of RINL during COVID-19

H₃= Health Care programmes are positive opinion of CSR initiatives of RINL during COVID-19

H₄= Skill Development programmes are positive opinion of CSR initiatives of RINL during COVID-19

H₅= Sanitation programmes are positive opinion of CSR initiatives of RINL during COVID-19

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research methodology is a systematic process that deals with identification of research problem, collection of facts or data, analyzing the data for reaching out a certain conclusion either in the form of solutions towards the problem encountered or certain generalizations for some theoretical formulations.

Primary Data

Primary data for the study was collected through a structured questionnaire which was prepared and circulated among the 120 respondents as a sample to elicit the perspectives of beneficiaries towards CSR initiatives of RINL during covid-19.

Secondary Data

The secondary data was gathered from the research studies conducted in the related areas in different universities and research institutions, books, journals, reviews of research publications, manuals, articles, bulletins and websites. It was also procured from the published reports of RINL, besides collecting statistical information from publications of Govt. of India and other agencies and institutions in India.

Data techniques:

The data thus collected was processed and analyzed with the help of statistical tools by employing latest version of SPSS 26.0. Percentages, mean and Standard Deviation. Given hypotheses have been tested by used Chi-square test. The chi-square test is testing the null hypothesis, which explained that there is difference between the expected and observed result.

CSR INITIATIVES OF RINL DURING COVID-19

In the month of March, 2020

- 1) An amount of Rs 116 lakhs was given towards PM-Cares Fund, for tackling the COVID-19 pandemic.

2)Education:

A) Akshaya Vidya: The 'Akshaya Vidya' programme which provides holistic education to the children in slum areas is progressing smoothly in all the 59 centers located in the slum areas of Visakhapatnam (19 centers), Hyderabad (25 centers) and YSR Kadapa (15 centers) Districts.

The 19 new centers of Visakhapatnam were inaugurated on 9th February 2020, with ED (HR-CS), VSP-RINL as Chief Guest. The tutors were distributed laptops and bags on this occasion.

CSR Executive visited some of the centers in Kadapa District, to monitor the progress of Activities. It was observed that the progress was satisfactory.

3) Health Care& Nutrition:

Cancer Screening: With support from VSP-RINL, Homi Bhabha Cancer Hospital & Research Centre (HBCHRC) has taken up a project for extending preventive healthcare service to 160 Mother-Daughter pairs, i.e., to 320 women. The project entails preventive vaccination of 160 girl students of 9th Standard of Visakha Vimala Vidyalayams located at Ukkunagaram & Pedagantyada and screening for cervical cancer/ breast cancer of their mothers. The activity is continuing.

4) Skill Development

Skill Development of persons affected by Leprosy/ Disability: VSP-RINL has taken up a project for one year residential Skill Development training program with The Leprosy Mission Trust India (TLMTI), Vizianagaram. Under this project, 25 persons affected by Leprosy/ Disability or those belonging to families affected by leprosy, are being trained in various courses viz. Computer Operation & Programming assistance, Diesel mechanic, Welder, Electrician and Dress making. The training is going on.

5). Sanitation:

Swachhata Pakhwada: In line with all CPSEs under Ministry of Steel, RINL observed Swachhata Pakhwada from 16th to 31st Mar 2020. Various Swachhata activities were carried out in the initial one week, thereafter, due to lock down, gatherings have been restricted.

Safai Pakhwada: Fortnight long intensive cleaning drives were organized in TTI, MDC & CC Depts during first fortnight and Sports and Vigilance depts. Observed in the second fortnight.

Swachh Bharat: "Shram Daan / Cleanliness drives carried out in various departments of VSP-

In the month of April, 2020

1) An amount of Rs 500 lakhs was given towards PM-Cares Fund, for tackling the COVID-19 pandemic.

2) From 31st Mar'2020 onwards, 600 packets of food on each day is being distributed for needy people (including migrant labor) in the surrounding villages of the Plant.

3) Education

Akshaya Vidya: The 'Akshaya Vidya' programme which provides holistic education is intended for the children in slum areas in 59 centers located in the slum areas of Visakhapatnam (19 centers), Hyderabad (25 centers) and YSR Kadapa (15 centers) Districts. CSR Executive visited some of the centres in Kadapa District, to monitor the progress of Activities. It was observed that the progress was satisfactory. Due to National Lockdown because of COVID-19 Pandemic, all the activities are suspended till the end of lockdown.

'Siksha': With a view that 'Education is a key enabler to social change' VSP- RINL is providing quality education to 1600 students belonging to BPL families from the surrounding villages of Plant and Mines..

4)Health Care& Nutrition:

A)Cancer Screening: With support from VSP-RINL, Homi Bhabha Cancer Hospital & Research Centre (HBCHRC) has taken up a project for extending preventive healthcare service to 160 Mother- Daughter pairs, i.e., to 320 women. The project entails preventive vaccination of 160 girl students of 9th Standard of Visakha Vimala Vidyalayams located at Ukkunagaram & Pedagantyada and screening for cervical cancer/ breast cancer of their mothers.

B).Approval was obtained for conducting 2 nos of Medical camps at MDM villages at an estimated cost of Rs 30,000/- and the same was communicated to Mines Department through IOM was done. Due to National Lockdown because of COVID-19 Pandemic, all the activities are suspended till the end of lockdown.

C)Mid-day Meals: Considering the dire need to extend nutritional support to children belonging to economically backward families, and tackle classroom hunger and resulting weakness and under nutrition, VSP-RINL through Akshaya Patra is providing Mid-day Meals to 900 needy students of the two Visakha Vimala Vidyalayas located at Ukkunagaram & Pedagantyada. Under the mid-day meal program unlimited, hot and nutritious mid-day meals, cooked with utmost hygiene and quality is being provided to school children on all school working days. Due to National Lockdown because of COVID-19 Pandemic, all the activities are suspended till the end of lockdown.

D)Infrastructural support for Centralized Kitchen, where mass cooking of Mid-day meals is carried out. These hot-cooked meals are packed in Stainless Steel containers and are sent to the schools through sterilized distribution vehicles. VSP-RINL is supporting the Akshaya Patra Foundation for laying CC road for dust-free environment within the kitchen premises and for procurement of Insulated Vessels for timely food distribution.

E)Adoption of destitute, abandoned Elderly: VSP-RINL adopted 50 abandoned and destitute elderly residents for a period of one year, through SHEOWS. The activity is going on.

5) Other Activities

A) Approval was obtained for carrying out Impact Assessment of 2 CSR Projects (Akshaya Vidya and Paatashala ki Aabharanam). Due to National Lockdown because of COVID-19 Pandemic, all the activities are suspended till the end of lockdown.

B) Parliament Questions and VIP References were replied expeditiously.

6) Skill Development

Skill Development of persons affected by Leprosy/ Disability: VSP-RINL has taken up a project for one year residential Skill Development training program with The Leprosy Mission Trust India (TLMTI), Vizianagaram. Under this project, 25 persons affected by Leprosy/ Disability or those belonging to families affected by leprosy, are being trained in various courses viz. Computer Operation & Programming assistance, Diesel mechanic, Welder, Electrician and Dress making. Due to National Lockdown because of COVID-19 Pandemic, all the activities are suspended till the end of lockdown.

7). Sanitation:

Safai Pakhwada schedule for the year 2020-21 was approved and circulated to the concerned departments. Due to COVID-19 pandemic, there was restricted and limited participation by maintaining social distancing at workplaces. As per the calendar, Safai Pakhwada was observed by CO&CCP and RMHP in the first fortnight and BF in the second fortnight.

In the month of May, 2020

I. Help during COVID-19 Pandemic:

Food Distribution to migrant workers: In order to help several migrant workers, daily wage labours who lost their livelihoods and were stranded away from their home, living around Visakhapatnam Steel Plant due to COVID-19 Pandemic, RINL –VSP has funded for distribution of 600 packets of food the needy people daily since 3-Apr-20, and continuing till end of May'2020(i.e. as lockdown is continuing) with an estimated expenditure of Rs 6.64 Lakhs including transportation (Daily two vehicles were arranged by RINL-VSP for the distribution of food). The beneficiaries include people belonging to the weaker sections, elderly people, migratory workers who lost their livelihoods due to the lockdown and their families and children from Odisha, Bihar, Jharkhand, etc. Throughout the process, all necessary precautions were taken and govt. guidelines for preventive measures were adhered to, such as, wearing masks, hand gloves, maintaining social distancing, using hand sanitizers, etc.

2. Education:

A) Akshaya Vidya: The 'Akshaya Vidya' programme which provides holistic education is intended for the children in slum areas in 59 centers located in the slum areas of Visakhapatnam (19 centers), Hyderabad (25 centers) and YSR Kadapa (15 centers) Districts. An Executive from CSR Dept visited some of the centers in Kadapa District, to monitor the progress of Activities. It was observed that the progress was satisfactory.

B) Arunodaya Special School: Arunodaya Special School run by Arunodaya Special School Educational Society was established in 1995 in a multi-category School center which caters to the children with learning impairment, mental retardation, cerebral palsy, autism, hearing loss and other learning disabilities. RINL-VSP has been extending financial support to the Arunodaya Special School Educational Society since beginning under CSR to meet the deficit expenditure of the school with a view to promote special education.

C) 'Siksha': With a view that 'Education is a key enabler to social change' VSP/RINL has been providing quality education to 1600 students belonging to BPL families from the surrounding villages of Plant and Mines.

D) Special repairs for Jr. College at V Madugula with an estimated cost of Rs 15.0 Lakhs has been taken up with AP Samagra Siksha Abhiyaan, Visakhapatnam.

E) Restoration of some of the Welfare Hostels in the 'Titli' cyclone affected areas of Srikakulam District has been taken up by extending financial assistance of Rs.25.00 Lakhs to the District Administration, Srikakulam.

3. Health Care:

A) Cancer Screening: With support from RINL-VSP, Homi Bhabha Cancer Hospital & Research Centre (HBCSRC) has taken up a project for extending preventive healthcare service to 160 Mother-Daughter pairs, i.e., to 320 women. The project entails preventive vaccination of 160 girl students of 9th Standard of Visakha Vimala Vidyalayams located at Ukkunagaram & Pedagantyada and screening for cervical cancer/ breast cancer of their mothers.

B) Medical Camps: An initiative is taken to conduct 2 no's of Medical camps at MDM villages at an estimated cost of Rs 30,000/- and they are kept on hold due to lockdown.

C) **Mid-day Meals:** Considering the dire need to extend nutritional support to children belonging to economically backward families, and tackle hunger during classes and resulting weakness and under nutrition, VSP-RINL through Akshaya Patra is providing Mid-day Meals to 900 needy students of the two Visakha Vimala Vidyalaya located at Ukkunagaram & Pedagantyada. Under the mid-day meal program unlimited, hot and nutritious mid-day meals, cooked with utmost hygiene and quality is being provided to school children on all school working days. Due to National Lockdown because of COVID-19 Pandemic, all the activities have been suspended and the same funds are diverted to distribute food packets to stranded workers/needy weaker sections affected by COVID-19

D) Infrastructural support for Centralized Kitchen, where mass cooking of Midday meals is carried out. These hot-cooked meals are packed in Stainless Steel containers and are sent to the schools through sterilized distribution vehicles. VSP-RINL is supporting the Akshaya Patra Foundation for laying CC road for dust free environment within the kitchen premises and for procurement of Insulated Vessels for timely food distribution.

E) **Adoption of destitute, abandoned Elderly:** VSP-RINL adopted 50 abandoned and destitute elderly residents for a period of one year, through SHEOWS. The activity is going on.

4. Skill Development:

Skill Development of persons affected by Leprosy/ Disability: VSP-RINL has taken up a project for one year residential Skill Development training program with The Leprosy Mission Trust India (TLMTI), Vizianagaram. Under this project, 25 persons affected by Leprosy/ Disability or those belonging to families affected by leprosy, are being trained in various courses viz. Computer Operation & Programming assistance, Diesel mechanic, Welder, Electrician and Dress making.

5. Other Activities

Impact Assessment: Impact Assessment of 2 CSR Projects (Akshaya Vidya and Paathashala Ki Aabharanam) has been taken up with NIT Rourkela.

6. Sanitation:

Safai Pakhwada: Due to lock down, there was restricted and limited participation by maintaining social distancing at workplaces. As per the calendar, Safai Pakhwada was observed by SMS-1, SMS-2, CRMP & RED in the first fortnight and TPP and SP in the second fortnight.

Swachh Bharat: 8 Shram Daan activities involving 81 employees were reported in the month. Emphasis was given on improving personal hygiene and sanitation at work places.

ANALYSIS OF THE STUDY

1.Level of satisfaction on Financial, social helping and other programmes			
OPTIONS	Sample		TOTAL
	Male	Female	
Extremely Satisfied	32	18	50
	(42)	(41)	(42)
Very Satisfied	20	13	33
	(26)	(29)	(28)
Moderately Satisfied	17	10	27
	(22)	(23)	(22)
Somewhat Satisfied	4	2	6
	(5)	(5)	(5)
Not at all Satisfied	3	1	4
	(4)	(2)	(3)
TOTAL	76	44	120
	(100)	(100)	(100)
Factor Value	3.97	4.2	3.99
R	0.99	0.99	-

	(0.00)	(0.000)	
Range	29	17	46
SD	12.07	7.2	19.3

Source: Primary Data

* Computed Values

The values in brackets indicate that Percentage of Response

Table-1 presents the percentage distribution of Financial, social helping and other programmes of RINL during the covid-19. The select respondent's feedback of about social services of RINL. Out of total sample 120; extremely satisfied 50(42 percent), 33(28 percent) very satisfied, 27 (22 percent) moderately satisfied, 6 (5 percent) somewhat satisfied and 4 (3 percent) are not at all satisfied. By taking male population out of 76, who were extremely satisfied 32(42 percent), 20(26 percent) very satisfied, 17 (22 percent) moderately satisfied, 4 (5 percent) somewhat satisfied and 3 (6 percent) are not at all satisfied. It can be seen from female sample; Out of 44 sample; extremely satisfied 18(41 percent), 13(29 percent) very satisfied, 10 (23 percent) moderately satisfied, 2 (5 percent) somewhat satisfied and 1 (2 percent) are not at all satisfied. It is observed both men and women have same satisfaction about this programme.

For statistical analysis; Factor score for male, female and total sample were 3.97, 4.2 and 3.99, which are closed associated; male population and female with total population. Both male and female were high positive correlation, Range opinion among male, female and were 29,17 and 46. For Standard Deviation male and female are 12.07 times and 7.2 times, which are long spread opinion with overall spread of total population i.e. 19.3times.

2.Level of satisfaction on Education Programmes			
OPTIONS	Sample		TOTAL
	Male	Female	
Extremely Satisfied	29	12	41
	(38)	(27)	(34)
Very Satisfied	21	19	40
	(28)	(43)	(34)
Moderately Satisfied	19	9	28
	(25)	(20)	(23)
Somewhat Satisfied	4	3	7
	(5)	(7)	(6)
Not at all Satisfied	3	1	4
	(4)	(2)	(3)
TOTAL	76	44	120
	(100)	(100)	(100)
Factor Value	3.91	3.86	3.89
R	0.97 (0.006)	0.93 (0.024)	-
Range	26	18	37
SD	16.32	7.23	17.67

Source: Primary Data

* Computed Values

The values in brackets indicate that Percentage of Response

Table-2 reveals the percentage distribution of Education programmes of RINL during the covid-19. The select respondent's feedback of about this service of RINL. Out of total sample 120; extremely satisfied 41(34 percent), 40(34 percent) very satisfied, 28 (23 percent) moderately satisfied, 7 (6 percent) somewhat satisfied and 4 (3 percent) are not at all satisfied. By considering male population out of 76, who were extremely satisfied 29(38 percent), 21(28 percent) very satisfied, 19 (25 percent) moderately satisfied, 4 (5 percent) somewhat satisfied and 3 (4 percent) are not at all satisfied. It can be seen from female sample; Out of 44 sample; extremely satisfied 12(27 percent), 19(43 percent) very satisfied, 9 (20 percent) moderately satisfied, 3 (7 percent) somewhat satisfied and 1 (2 percent) are not at all satisfied. It is observed both men and women have 93% to 97% satisfaction about this programme.

For statistical analysis; Factor score for male, female and total sample were 3.91, 3.86 and 3.89, which all most equally associated; male population and female with total population. Both male and female were high positive Correlation, Range

opinion among male, female and were 26,18 and 37. For Standard Deviation male and female are 12.7 times and 7.2 times, which are too long spread opinion with overall spread of total population i.e. 17.67 times.

3.Level of satisfaction on Health Care Programmes			
OPTIONS	Sample		TOTAL
	Male	Female	
Extremely Satisfied	13	13	26
	(17)	(30)	(22)
Very Satisfied	26	11	37
	(34)	(25)	(31)
Moderately Satisfied	21	16	37
	(28)	(36)	(31)
Somewhat Satisfied	12	3	15
	(16)	(7)	(13)
Not at all Satisfied	4	1	5
	(5)	(2)	(4)
TOTAL	76	44	120
	(100)	(100)	(100)
Factor Value	3.42	3.73	3.53
R	0.72	0.85	-
	(0.166)	(0.069)	
Range	22	15	32
SD	8.52	6.49	14

Source: Primary Data

* Computed Values

The values in brackets indicate that Percentage of Response

Table-3: It can be seen the percentage distribution of Health Care programmes of RINL during the covid-19. The selected sample response of about this service of RINL. Out of total sample 120; extremely satisfied 22(26 percent), 37(31 percent) very satisfied, 37 (31 percent) moderately satisfied, 15 (13 percent) somewhat satisfied and 5 (4 percent) are not at all satisfied. By seeing male population out of 76, who were extremely satisfied 13(17 percent), 26(34 percent) very satisfied, 21 (28 percent) moderately satisfied, 12 (16 percent) somewhat satisfied and 4 (5 percent) are not at all satisfied. It can be seen from female sample; Out of 44 sample; extremely satisfied 13(30 percent), 11(25 percent) very satisfied, 16 (36 percent) moderately satisfied, 3 (7 percent) somewhat satisfied and 1 (2 percent) are not at all satisfied. It is observed both men and women have 72% to 85% satisfaction about this programme.

For statistical analysis; Factor score for male, female and total sample were 3.42, 3.73 and 3.53, which all most equally associated; male population and female with total population. Both male and female were positive Correlation, Range opinion among male, female and were 22,15 and 32. For Standard Deviation male and female are 8.52 times and 6.49 times, which are too long spread opinion with overall spread of total population 14 as standard deviation.

4.Level of satisfaction on Skill Development Programmes			
OPTIONS	Sample		TOTAL
	Male	Female	
Extremely Satisfied	18	15	33
	(24)	(34)	(28)
Very Satisfied	29	18	47
	(38)	(41)	(39)
Moderately Satisfied	19	7	26
	(25)	(16)	(22)
Somewhat Satisfied	8	2	10
	(11)	(4)	(8)
Not at all Satisfied	2	2	4
	(3)	(4)	(3)
TOTAL	76	44	120
	(100)	(100)	(100)

Factor Value	3.7	3.95	3.79
R	0.98 (0.003)	0.96 (0.009)	-
Range	27	16	43
SD	10.43	7.39	17.39

Source: Primary Data

* Computed Values

The values in brackets indicate that Percentage of Response

Table-4: reveals that the percentage distribution of Skill Development programmes of RINL during the covid-19. The selected sample response of about this service of RINL. Out of total sample 120; extremely satisfied 33(28 percent), 47(39 percent) very satisfied, 26 (22 percent) moderately satisfied, 10 (8 percent) somewhat satisfied and 4 (3 percent) are not at all satisfied. By taking male population out of 76, who were extremely satisfied 18(24 percent), 29(38 percent) very satisfied, 19 (25 percent) moderately satisfied, 8 (11 percent) somewhat satisfied and 2 (3 percent) are not at all satisfied. It can be seen from female sample; Out of 44 sample; extremely satisfied 15(34 percent), 18(41 percent) very satisfied, 7 (16 percent) moderately satisfied, 2 (4 percent) somewhat satisfied and 2 (4 percent) are not at all satisfied. It is observed both men and women have same satisfaction about this programme.

For statistical analysis; Factor score for male, female and total sample were 3.70, 3.95 and 3.79, which all most extremely associated; male population and female with total population. Both male and female were positive high Correlation, Range opinion among male, female and were 27,16 and 43. For Standard Deviation male and female are 10.43 times and 7.39 times, which are too long spread opinion with overall spread of total population 17.39 times as standard deviation.

5.Level of satisfaction on Sanitation Programmes			
OPTIONS	Sample		TOTAL
	Male	Female	
Extremely Satisfied	13	16	29
	(17)	(36)	(24)
Very Satisfied	21	19	40
	(28)	(43)	(33)
Moderately Satisfied	28	6	34
	(37)	(14)	(28)
Somewhat Satisfied	10	1	11
	(13)	(2)	(25)
Not at all Satisfied	4	2	6
	(5)	(4)	(5)
TOTAL	76	44	120
	(100)	(100)	(100)
Factor Value	3.38	4.5	3.63
R	0.86 (0.061)	0.89 (0.041)	-
Range	24	18	34
SD	9.41	8.08	14.78

Source: Primary Data

* Computed Values

The values in brackets indicate that Percentage of Response

Table-5: It can be seen the percentage distribution of Sanitation programmes of RINL during the covid-19. The selected sample response of about this service of RINL. Out of total sample 120; extremely satisfied 29(24 percent), 40(33 percent) very satisfied, 34 (28 percent) moderately satisfied, 11 (25 percent) somewhat satisfied and 6 (5 percent) are not at all satisfied. By seeing male population out of 76, who were extremely satisfied 13(17 percent), 21(28 percent) very satisfied, 28 (37 percent) moderately satisfied, 10 (13 percent) somewhat satisfied and 4 (5 percent) are not at all satisfied. It can be seen from female sample; Out of 44 sample; extremely satisfied 16(36 percent), 19(43 percent) very satisfied, 6 (14 percent) moderately satisfied, 1 (2 percent) somewhat satisfied and 2 (4 percent) are not at all satisfied. It is observed both men and women have 86% to 89% satisfaction about this programme.

For statistical analysis it is observed that Factor score for male, female and total sample were 3.38, 4.5 and 3.63, which all not equally associated; male population and female with total population. Both male and female were positive Correlation, Range opinion among male, female and were 24, 18 and 34. For Standard Deviation male and female are 9.41 times and 8.08 times, which are too long spread opinion with overall spread of total population 14.78 ties as standard deviation.

CHI-SQUARE ANALYSIS

This chi-square measures to compare a collection of definite data with some hypothetical expected distribution. It is a statistical test commonly used to compare observed data with data we would expect to obtain according to a specific hypothesis. The chi-square test is testing the null hypothesis, which explained that there is no difference between the expected and observed result. This point of study is to find the positive impact of CSR initiatives to their personnel life in selected RINL is taken five hypotheses, which are tested by using chi-square test by considered demographic variables and other variables:

The formula for calculating chi-square = $(O - E)^2 / E$.

Table- 6: Testing of hypotheses between CSR initiatives and Personnel Life

CHI-SQUARE ANALYSIS

HYPOTHESES	Chi-Square	Hypothesis Result	Significance
H ₁ = Financial assistance, social helping and other programmes are positive opinion of CSR initiatives of RINL during COVID -19.	0.38	Accepted	0.9999
H ₂ = Education programmes are positive opinion of CSR initiatives of RINL during COVID-19	3.58	Accepted	0.8925
H ₃ = Health Care programmes are positive opinion of CSR initiatives of RINL during COVID-19	5.83	Accepted	0.6653
H ₄ = Skill Development programmes are positive opinion of CSR initiatives of RINL during COVID-19	3.72	Accepted	0.8817
H ₅ = Sanitation programmes are positive opinion of CSR initiatives of RINL during COVID-19	15.22	Rejected	0.0549

* Significant at 5% level, the result is not significant at $p < 0.05$. Critical Value at 5% is 11.07

Source: Computed

Inference: It can be seen from the above table shows the chi-square values of given five hypotheses of study is relating to CSR initiatives of RINL. By applied Chi-square test, it is indicated all variables are positively impact except variable five on the CSR initiatives of RINL at 5% level of significance. Hence it can be seen financial assistance, social helping and other programmes, Education programmes, Health care programmes and Skill development programmes are positively and Sanitation programmes is negatively impact on the CSR initiatives of RINL. Further it is concluded that out of five CSR social helping programmes, which are initiated by RINL people have expressed high satisfaction and positive opinion except sanitation programmes during COVID-19 period.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

Corporate Social Responsibility initiatives undertaken by RINL has benefited, the people who are residing in villages at plant, the welfare programmes are education, health care, skill development, financial assistance and sanitation are initiatives help poor through welfare schemes during pandemic situation of covid-19. This point of study gets findings, which are

- It is known that an amount of Rs 116 lakhs was given towards PM-Cares Fund, for tackling the COVID-19 pandemic.
- An amount of Rs 500 lakhs was given towards PM-Cares Fund, for tackling the COVID-19 pandemic.
- During COVID-19 Locking from 31st Mar'2020 onwards, 600 packets of food on each day is being distributed for needy people (including migrant labor) in the surrounding villages of the Plant.

- Approval was obtained for carrying out Impact Assessment of 2 CSR Projects (Akshaya Vidya and Paatashala ki Aabharanam). Due to National Lockdown because of COVID-19 Pandemic, all the activities are suspended till the end of lockdown.
- Swachhata Pakhwada: In line with all CPSEs under Ministry of Steel, RINL observed Swachhata Pakhwada from 16th to 31st Mar 2020. Various Swachhata activities were carried out in the initial one week, thereafter, due to lock down, gatherings have been restricted.
- Safai Pakhwada' schedule for the year 2020-21 was approved and circulated to the concerned departments. Due to COVID-19 pandemic, there was restricted and limited participation by maintaining social distancing at workplaces. As per the calendar, Safai Pakhwada was observed by CO&CCP and RMHP in the first fortnight and BF in the second fortnight.
- It is observed that out of five CSR social helping programmes of RINL that The beneficiaries who have expressed high satisfaction and positive opinion except sanitation programmes during COVID-19 period.
- It is found that Education programmes, Health care programmes and Skill development programmes are continues programmes, which are temporarily hold due to COVID -19 impact.

Every corporate has come forward to overcoming this pandemic situation as a corporate social responsibility to give financial assistance, helping hands and support to common people and government. This is an adverse situation over coming to share responsibility by well-established corporates, entities and companies in India. We must follow the initiations of RINL as a corporate social responsibility.

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